

Evaluation of Mechanical Properties of Hollow Steel in Timor-Leste Market

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Abstract: Hollow steel is a significant material, which are used for the roof, windows, and doors frame, and sometimes used for the structural of building. It gives buildings a better strength-to-weight ratio. Therefore, in this research the physical material and quality of mechanical properties of hollow steel were studied. The sample taken from different suppliers (Indonesia and Chinese supplier) in Timor-Leste were investigated and evaluated. Yield strength, tensile strength and effective thickness of the samples were compared to the requirement value to the American standard.

Keywords: Hollow steel, steel quality, yield strength, tensile strength, effective thickness.

1. Introduction

Hollow steel is one of the materials normally used for the roof, windows and doors frame, sometimes used for structural building and other construction purposes. It gives buildings a better strength-to-weight ratio. Therefore, the quality of the hollow steel is mostly required. It is important to know the physical and mechanical properties of the materials through the experiments. The physical properties of materials are examined through the thickness, width and cross section area [1,2]. Meanwhile, the mechanical property is through the yields strength, tensile strength and ratio of tensile strength and yield strength, and elongation were compared to ASTM A500[3].

The standard of American Society of Testing Materials (ASTM) has usually been used in Timor-Leste due to the lack of the Timor-Leste's own standard for controlling the imported construction materials. On the other hand, the Quality Control commission does not establish yet, therefore the materials are distributed in Timor-Leste market without meticulous information.

In the previous study, the quality of reinforcement bar in Timor-Leste market is investigated [4] and new study relevant to the quality of the material is mostly needed

While in this research the same study is done to the hollow steel that were collected from four shops (S1, S2, S3, S4) in Dili city

(Timor Leste). The material was tested in tension and the results were compared to the specification by ASTM A500 [2,3] and finally the quality of hollow steel distributed in Timor-Leste is investigated.

2. Experimental Studies

Tensile test was carried out in laboratory of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Science and Technology, Universidade Nacional Timor Lorosa'e. The specification of the hydraulic system of universal tensile testing machine and supported equipment are shown in table

1 and Fig. 1(a) and (b). Two tensile test machines are used, due to the differences on materials compatibility.

Fig. 2 shows the shape of material used for the test and the dimension of the material is shown in table 2. The specimen with the standard dimension was tested on the universal tensile test machine, while the specimen with the sub size dimension was tested on the Minibea tensile test machine. The data logger with the model GL900 was installed to the universal tensile test machine for the data recording.

a. Universal tensile test machine.

b. Minibea tensile test machine.

Fig. 1 Tensile test machine.

Table 1 Tensile machine and device.

Universal tensile testing machine	MRA-F2 Series (Maekawa)	500 kN (maximum load)
Tensile and compression testing machine	Minibea TGI-5 kN	5 kN (maximum load)
Data logger	midi LOGGER TYPE GL900-4	Graphtec Corporation Made in China

Fig. 2 The shape of the material test.

Table 2 Dimensions of the specimens.

	Dimensions	
	Standard specimens	Sub size specimen
	Plate-type,	
	40 mm[1.500 in.] wide	6 mm[0.250 in.] wide
	mm[in.]	
G- Gauge length	200.00 ± 0.2 [8.00±0.01]	25.0±0.1 [1.000 ± 0.0031]
W—Width	40.0 ± 2.0 [1.500 ± 0.125, - 0.250]	6.0 ± 0.1
	Thickness of material	
R—Radius of fillet, mm	25 [1]	6 [0.250]
L—Overall length, mm	450[18]	100[4]
A—Length of reduced section, mm	225[9]	32[1.25]
B—Length of grip section, mm	75[9]	30[1.25]
C—Width of grip section, approximate	50[2]	10[0.375]

For the comparison study, the material from different shops such as Indonesian and Chinese shops were collected. They are namely S1, S2, S3 and S4. The hollow steel with two differences size (30*30 mm and 40*40 mm) and class (class A and B) were collected. The materials from each shop

have different quality in term of TS, YS and thickness.

3. Test Results

Table 3 shows the experimental result of the hollow steel materials from shop S1 with the dimension 30*30 mm and 40*40 mm categorize into class A and B. For materials with class A, the tested result shows the yield strength (YS) of material 30*30 mm

is 448.49 MPa, while tensile strength (TS) is 483.76 MPa and TS/YS ratio is 1.09. For the material 40*40 mm, the YS is 430.56 MPa, TS is 487.80 MPa and the TS/YS ratio is 1.13. On the other hand, the materials categorize with class B, the YS, TS and TS/YS ratio of materials 30*30 mm is 175.01 MPa, 449.36

MPa and 2.59, respectively. For the material 40*40 mm, the YS is 231.52 MPa, TS is 395.56 MPa and TS/YS ratio is 1.71. The TS/YS ratio of hollow steel 30*30 mm is higher than 1.25.

Table 3. Experimental result for the hollow steel of the test by S1 Shop.

40*40 A									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	1.60	12.05	19.28	8.66	449.17	9.70	503.11	1.12	9.60
2.00	1.59	12.33	19.60	8.21	418.78	9.10	464.17	1.11	9.60
3.00	1.59	12.69	20.18	8.55	423.75	10.01	496.11	1.17	11.50
Average	1.59	12.36	19.69	8.47	430.56	9.60	487.80	1.13	10.23
40*40 B									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	1.41	6.82	9.62	2.16	224.93	3.81	396.52	1.76	0.16
2.00	1.53	6.84	10.47	2.57	245.86	3.87	369.99	1.50	0.13
3.00	1.44	6.53	9.40	2.10	223.75	3.95	420.18	1.88	0.14
Average	1.46	6.73	9.83	2.28	231.52	3.88	395.56	1.71	0.14
30*30 A									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	1.73	12.75	22.06	9.83	445.65	10.12	458.80	1.03	6.71
2.00	1.81	12.74	23.06	10.35	448.84	11.63	504.35	1.12	6.67
3.00	1.81	12.05	21.81	9.64	441.99	10.66	488.76	1.11	10.14
Average	1.78	12.51	22.31	9.94	445.49	10.80	483.76	1.09	7.84
30*30 B									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1	1.53	6.68	10.22	1.78	174.36	4.90	479.63	2.75	0.09
2	1.55	6.81	10.56	2.03	191.84	4.47	423.57	2.21	0.15
3	1.52	6.81	10.35	1.64	158.82	4.61	444.88	2.80	0.38

Average	1.53	6.77	10.38	1.82	175.01	4.66	449.36	2.59	0.21
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Table 4 experimental result for the hollow steel of the test by S2 Shop.

40*40 A									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	1.45	6.31	9.15	2.03	221.43	3.50	382.97	1.73	0.06
2.00	1.44	6.61	9.52	1.53	160.22	3.52	369.49	2.31	0.19
3.00	1.45	6.29	9.12	2.26	247.79	3.81	417.41	1.68	0.38
Average	1.45	6.40	9.26	1.94	209.81	3.61	389.96	1.86	0.21
40*40 B									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	0.88	6.26	5.51	1.23	223.46	2.16	392.64	1.76	0.07
2.00	1.00	6.16	6.16	1.55	251.62	1.91	310.71	1.23	0.24
3.00	1.01	6.03	6.09	1.36	223.14	2.19	359.42	1.61	0.14
Average	0.96	6.15	5.92	1.38	232.74	2.09	354.26	1.52	0.15
30*30 A									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	1.45	6.36	9.22	2.24	242.57	3.81	413.47	1.70	0.32
2.00	1.45	6.38	9.25	2.31	249.59	4.14	447.74	1.79	0.35
3.00	1.49	6.49	9.67	2.32	240.23	4.01	415.09	1.73	0.13
Average	1.46	6.10	9.38	2.29	244.13	3.99	425.43	1.74	0.27
30*30 B									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	0.78	6.21	4.84	1.53	314.84	2.16	445.11	1.41	0.16
2.00	0.80	6.09	4.87	2.57	528.12	3.87	794.75	1.50	0.10
3.00	0.97	6.01	5.83	1.56	267.08	2.01	344.79	1.29	0.35
Average	0.85	6.10	5.18	1.89	370.01	2.68	528.21	1.43	0.20

Table 4 shows the experimental result of the materials hollow steel from shop S2 of materials with the dimension 30*30 mm and 40*40 mm categorize with class B. The YS of material 30*30 mm is 370.01 MPa, TS is

528.21 MPa and TS/YS ratio is 1.43. For the material 40*40 mm, the YS is 232.74 MPa, TS is 354.26 MPa and TS/YS ratio is 1.52. On the other hand, for the materials categorize with class A, the YS for the

material 30*30mm is 244.13 MPa, TS is 425.43 MPa and TS/TY ratio is 1.74. For the material 40*40 mm, the YS is 209.81 MPa, TS is 389.96 MPa and TS/YS ratio is 1.86.

Table 5 shows the experimental result of the materials hollow steel from shop S3 of

materials with the dimension 30*30 mm and 40*40 mm categorize with class B. The YS of material 30*30 mm is 257.95 MPa, TS is 421.22 MPa and TS/YS ratio is 1.63. For the material 40*40 mm, the YS is 287.71 MPa, TS is 405.70 MPa and TS/YS ratio is 1.41.

Table 5 Experimental result for the hollow steel of the test by S3 Shop.

40*40 B									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	1.51	6.16	9.30	2.92	313.39	3.82	410.68	1.31	0.08
2.00	1.61	6.55	10.55	2.61	247.40	4.31	408.99	1.65	0.39
3.00	1.60	6.52	10.43	3.15	302.34	4.15	397.43	1.31	0.09
Average	1.57	6.41	10.09	2.89	287.71	4.09	405.70	1.41	0.19
30*30 B									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	Mpa	kN	Mpa		mm
1.00	1.24	6.26	7.76	1.63	209.47	3.10	399.88	1.91	0.21
2.00	1.25	6.16	7.70	2.03	263.38	3.45	448.31	1.70	0.39
3.00	1.33	6.03	8.02	2.41	301.00	3.33	415.47	1.38	0.14
Average	1.27	6.15	7.83	2.02	257.95	3.30	421.22	1.63	0.24

Table 6 shows the experimental result of the materials hollow steel from shop S4 of materials with the dimension 30*30 mm and 40*40 mm categorize with class B. The YS

of material 30*30 mm is 286.27 MPa, TS is 399.05 MPa and TS/YS ratio is 1.39. For the material 40*40 mm, the YS is 193.14 MPa, TS is 330.98 MPa and the TS/YS ratio is 1.71.

Table 6 Experimental result for the hollow steel by the shop S4.

40*40 B									
No. of Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	1.18	6.38	7.53	1.49	198.32	2.64	350.54	1.77	0.12
2.00	1.18	6.09	7.19	1.43	199.55	1.91	266.34	1.33	0.28
3.00	1.18	6.40	7.55	1.37	181.54	2.84	376.06	2.07	0.37
Average	1.18	6.29	7.42	1.43	193.14	2.46	330.98	1.71	0.26

30*30 B									
Sample	Thickness	Width	Area	Yield load	Yield strength	Tensile load	Tensile strength	TS/YS Ratio	Stroke
	mm	mm	mm ²	kN	MPa	kN	MPa		mm
1.00	0.88	6.18	5.44	1.71	314.25	2.35	431.38	1.37	0.12
2.00	1.00	6.21	6.21	1.55	249.60	2.41	388.08	1.55	0.09
3.00	1.01	6.20	6.26	1.85	294.95	2.37	377.67	1.28	0.13
Average	0.96	6.20	5.97	1.70	286.27	2.37	399.05	1.39	0.11

4. Comparison with Specifications

Fig. 3 show the experimental result of YS and TS of hollow steel materials with the dimension 30*30 mm that categorize into class A and B from shop S1, S2, S3 and S4. Fig. 3(a) shows the experimental result of the material of class A. The tested result shows that the YS and TS of material from shop S1 and S2 is different of 43 % and 8 %, respectively. The experimental result of the materials for the class B is shown in Fig. 3(b). The tested result shows that the YS and TS of the materials from Shop S1, S2, S3 and S4

are significantly different. The higher value of TS and YS is the material from shop S2. The percentages difference of TS from shop S2 to the materials from shop S1, S3 and S4 is 16.13 %, 20.5 % and 24.5 %, respectively. While, the percentage differences of YS from shop S2 to the material from shop S1, S3 and S4 is 52.7 %, 30.3 % and 22.7 %, respectively. It is observed that the mechanical properties for those materials have different grades (A, B, C, and D) based on the ASTM A500/A500M-13 [3].

Fig. 3 Experimental result of yield and tensile strength of the hollow steel 30*30.

a. Experimental result of hollow steel class A.

b. Experimental result of hollow steel class B.

Fig. 4 Experimental result of yield and tensile strength of the hollow steel 40*40.

Fig. 4 shows the experimental result of YS and TS of the hollow steel 40*40 mm with class A and B from shop S1, S2, S3 and S4. Fig. 4(a) shows the experimental result of the material for the class A. The tested result shows that the difference of the YS and TS of material from shop S1 and S2 is 46.2 % and 12 %, respectively. Fig. 4(b) shows the experimental result of the materials for the class B. The tested result shows that the YS and TS of the materials from Shop S1, S2, S3 and S4 are significantly different. Shop 3 has higher the TS and. The different percentage of TS to material from shop S1, S2 and S4 is 2.5 %, 13 % and 18.5 %, respectively. On the other hand, the differences between higher YS from shop S3 to the material from shop S1, S2 and S4 is 19.5 %, 18.8 % and 32.9 %, respectively. It is noticed that the mechanical properties for

those materials have different grades (A, B, C, and D) based on the ASTM A500/A500M-13 [3].

Fig. 5 shows the experimental results of the thickness of hollow steel material 30*30 mm of class A and B from shop S1, S2, S3 and S4. Fig. 5(a) shows the thickness of the material for the class A. The tested result shows that the thickness of material from shop S1 and S2 is 1.78 mm and 1.46 mm, respectively. Fig. 5(b) shows the thickness of the materials of class B. The tested result shows that the thickness of the materials from shop S1, S2, S3 and S4 is 1.53 mm, 0.85 mm, 1.27 mm, 0.96 mm, respectively. It is noticed that the distributed materials are different in term of physical material and mechanical properties, while some did not meet the standard [1-3].

a. Thickness material of class A.

b. Thickness material of class B.

Fig. 5 The thickness of the steel hollow 30*30.

a. Thickness material of class A.

b. Thickness material of class B.

Fig. 6 the thickness of the hollow steel 40*40.

Fig. 6 shows the experimental results of the thickness of hollow steel material 40*40 mm of class A and B from shop S1, S2, S3 and S4. Fig. 6(a) shows the thickness of the material of class A. The tested result shows that the thickness of material from shop S1 and S2 is 1.59 mm and 1.45 mm, respectively. Fig. 6(b) shows the thickness of the materials

class B. The tested result shows that the thickness of the materials from Shop S1, S2, S3 and S4 is 1.46 mm, 0.96 mm, 1.57 mm, 1.18 mm, respectively. It is noticed that the distributed materials are different in term of physical materials and mechanical properties, while some did not meet the standard [1-3]

5. Conclusions

Yield strength, Tensile strength, thickness of the hollow steel were investigated. The quality of the hollow steel distributed in Timor-Leste market is investigated and

evaluated. The tested result showed that most of the hollow steel materials have different physical properties and mechanical properties, while some of material did not meet the standard value.

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